

Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) Dialogues in Thailand

“Together we can: Synergising our efforts to overcome “AMR” the Silent Epidemic”

Date: 14th – 16th December 2021

Venue: Pullman Khon Kaen Raja Orchid Hotel

Agenda

Time	Topic
Day 1: (14th Dec 2021): Facilitator: Chaiwat Thirapantu	
8:30 - 9:00	Registration
9:00 – 9:10	Introduction of the project
9:10 – 9:45	<p>In a relaxing atmosphere, participants sit in a big circle.</p> <p>Check-in process and ice breaking: Following mindful breathing for a while to slow down the mind and get ready for deep learning dialogue. One by one, participants introduce themselves and speak out their intention in attending this Conversation.</p> <p>Introducing facilitating team by chief facilitator Chaiwat Thirapantu</p> <p>Clarifying context and intention, a brief introduction on AMR highlighting the case of Samuthsakorn governor, a survivor of Covid-19 and AMR</p>
9:45 – 10:45	<p>Group conversation:</p> <p>Reality check in community: In a group of 4-5 people, take turn sharing personal practice as well as observation towards pharmaceutical consumption in family, relatives, and communities.</p> <p>With mind mapping technique, put the group ideas on flipcharts to demonstrate an overview of medicine intake behavior in communities.</p> <p>Reality check with an AMR expert Associate Professor Direk Limmathurotsakul</p> <p>Read provided handouts on “AMR situation and scenario in Thailand” then discuss in groups; “why our collaboration is crucial in coping AMR and in bringing the National AMR Strategy to fruition?”</p> <p>Post-it your ideas: After group discussion, on a post-it, write down one’s reflection on the significance of effective AMR implementation, Put together all individual insights on a flipchart as collective understanding and share it with other groups.</p>

10:45 – 11:00	<i>Coffee break</i>
11:00 – 12:00	Reflecting insights with the Facilitator: Sitting in one big circle, participants reflect their insights with facilitator Chaiwat.
12:00 – 13:00	<i>lunch</i>
13:00 – 14:30	<p>Mindful movement activity to get participants energized after lunch</p> <p>Group conversation: Contemplate on Rational Drug Use (RDU)</p> <p>(For non-health participants) “Have you ever heard or been told of RDU? If you have, who gave you the information? Have you ever known or be warned about the risks of inappropriate medicine intake? If you have, who delivered that information to you?”</p> <p>(For health-related professionals such as pharmacists, primary health care volunteers, doctors, nurses) “How have you been engaging in the RDU policy and implementation? And what have you done to ensure RDU sustainability in community? What are your major obstacles and concerns regarding RDU so far?”</p>
14:30 – 14:45	<i>Coffee break</i>
14:45 – 16:00	Continuing group activity: Put the group ideas on flipcharts, illustrating each individual’s shared stories on RDU.
16:00 – 17:30	Movie Inspired: Watch “ Contagion ”, the 2011 American film directed by Steven Soderbergh which plots a scenario of worldwide viral outbreak and attempts of researchers, medical professionals to curb the pandemic.
18.00	<i>Leisure time</i>

Time	Topic
Day 2: (15th Dec 2021): Facilitator: Chaiwat Thirapantu	
8:30-9:00	Registration
9:00 – 9:20	Check-in routine: Following mindful breathing to still the mind and get ready for generative conversation.
9:20 – 10:30	Group conversation: “What have you learned from the movie, specifically regarding the degradation of ecological system that brings about the pandemic (in the movie)?”
10:30 – 10:45	<i>Coffee break</i>
10:45 - 12:00	<p>Group conversation: Feasibility of AMR in Primary Healthcare System and District Health Board</p> <p>Facilitator inputs on existing structures under the Ministry of Public Health’s administration; the Primary healthcare system which has produced community health volunteers in every district nationwide; and the more recent body called the District Health Board which focuses on participatory approach to involve community members to frame their health problems and collaborate in the solutions in order to promote healthy lifestyles in communities.</p> <p>In this respect, “How would we push the envelope, incorporating “AMR” in Primary Healthcare System and District Health Board?” Please share concrete ideas on plausible actions.</p>
12:00 – 13:00	<i>lunch</i>
13:00 – 14:45	<p>Group conversation: Following the visions and missions of Primary Health Care System and District Health Board respecting food safety, how can we incorporate AMR into our work and life to promote food safety (free from AMR)?</p> <p>Group work: Share tangible ideas that can be implemented. Put all ideas on flipcharts. Share your group ideas with other groups.</p>
14:45 – 15:00	<i>Coffee break</i>
15:00 -16:30	Group conversation: Finding the gaps

	<p>As active citizen, health professionals, spiritual leaders, teachers and so on, all of us aspire to see a healthy community, what would then be your suggestions or proposals to top executives, high ranking administrators for instance, to support and sustain your vision systematically?”</p> <p>Contemplate on the “missing links” or “loopholes” in healthcare system in the past, especially on AMR issue? List them down as many as possible, and describe your reasons why those links matter and how should they be tackled.</p> <p>Share your thoughts with the group members. Then put all ideas on flipchart.</p>
16:30	Leisure time

Time	Topic
Day 3: (16th Dec 2021): Facilitator: Chaiwat Thirapantu	
8:30-9:00	Registration
9:00 – 9:20	Check-in routine: Following mindful breathing to still the mind and get ready for generative conversation.
9:20 – 10:45	<p>Fishbowl conversation:</p> <p>Facilitator Chaiwat inputs: In the 8th National Health Assembly, held in December 2015, the congregation discussed and later proposed the 5th Resolution addressing “Crisis of AMR and Integrated AMR Solution Implementation”.</p> <p>Thailand’s National Strategic Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance comprises of 6 strategies, as follows;</p> <p>Strategy 1 AMR surveillance system using “One-Health” approach</p> <p>Strategy 2 Regulation of antimicrobial distribution</p> <p>Strategy 3 Infection prevention and control and antimicrobial stewardship in humans</p> <p>Strategy 4 AMR prevention and control and antimicrobial stewardship in agriculture and animals</p> <p>Strategy 5 Public knowledge on AMR and awareness of appropriate use of antimicrobials</p> <p>Strategy 6 Governance mechanisms to develop and sustain AMR-related actions</p> <p>From the above information and what we have been discussing so far, what are your big ideas for us to realize AMR Strategy 5th and 6th? How can your ideas be integrated to provincial health assembly? What will you do to make impacts in your community?</p> <p>(Fishbowl is a participatory technique to facilitate a big group conversation. A small number of participants, 4-5 people, will be asked to sit in an inner circle and engage in AMR deep discussion with facilitator Chaiwat, the rest of participants, in an outer circle, are active observers. After a while, all participants will be asked to break into small groups and join the discussion. The inner circle conversation serves as a springboard to a deeper discussion in small groups.)</p>

10:45 – 11:00	<i>Coffee break</i>
11:00 - 12:00	Feedbacks: In a feedback form, please write your observations, suggestions and your lessons learned and insights that you get so far from the conversation.
12:00 – 13:00	<i>lunch</i>
13:00 – 14:30	<p>Group conversation and work: Co-creating a six-month plan ahead</p> <p>In a group of same or neighbouring provinces, exchange your thoughts as follows</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Tell your group members about your skills, talents, interests, and passions. What and how can you exercise your strengths to realize AMR solutions, nationally and locally? 2) Name persons, groups, or organisations that you think are and can be strong alliance to work on AMR with you. Why do they matter? 3) Prioritise 5 tasks, areas, issues that you would do to tackle AMR problems after this Conversation
14:30-14:45	<i>Coffee break</i>
14:45 – 15:30	Continuing group work: Co-creating AMR community of commitment in the region
15:30-16:00	Check out from conversation
16:00	Have a safe trip home!

**** Please note that the schedule is subject to change.**